

MAGNETIC RESONANCE IMAGING

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Annotation: Magnetic Resonance Imaging is the use of this effect to stimulate radio rays into the human body, create a strong magnetic field and record the body's response to electromagnetic radiation. The result of these processes is the creation of the image by processing the incoming signal on the computer.

Key words: MRT, proton, contrast agent, Faraday cage, spinal cord, brain, procedure, oncology, coils, gadolinium

Magnetic resonance imaging scanning allows you to achieve a high-precision diagnosis, detect changes in body work and produce high-precision visualization of the organs under study (an imaginary image of the target). This procedure allows you to measure the speed of blood flow, the movement of cerebrospinal fluid, to identify oncology and a number of other diseases and dangerous pathologies. The operation of the device is based on the principle of NMR, further processing the received data. An important factor explaining the operation of the device is the presence of protons in the human body.

During the procedure for MRT diagnostics, ionizing radiation is not used, but electromagnetic waves that are safe for the human body are used.

Modern MRT equipment consists of the following parts:

- magnetic
- coils (reel) wrapped in magnetic tap

-A device that produces Radio impulses

-Faraday cage (a box made of high-permeable metal with walls).

Physical impact manifests itself in the influence of an external factor on the cell.

Its role is electromagnetic radiation.

-Power supply - Cooling system

-A system that serves to process incoming data MRT spiral

-designed to improve the uniformity of the magnetic field.

Stream through themselves and adapt to compensate for the lack of uniformity.

Transmitter at MRT (element processing principle in tomography system) - this device radiofrequency generates vibration and impulse. Such a modification allows to achieve the excitation of the cores, to influence the contrast of the etched image. The receiver at MRT(element processing principle in tomography system) is an ultra-high frequency operating high sensitivity and low noise signal change the recording voice from MHz to kHz (high frequency to low frequency). Examination of the patient in magnetic resonance imaging.

The patient is inserted into a narrow hole in a horizontal position. In the pipe, a strong magnetic field of the device is affected. To the central part of the device, the body must be properly positioned so that the body is examined. The leak lasts 15-20 minutes and the image comes out. It is created using the NMR method, which is a physical phenomenon of nuclear magnetic resonance associated with the properties of protons. The radiation generated in the electromagnetic field created by the device using the Radio frequency pulse is generated it turns into a signal. Then it is registered and processed through a computer program.

Since the human body consists of 65-90% of water, the protons of hydrogen atoms are stimulated. This method of exposure makes it possible to detect serious diseases without the eyes and physical intervention of the body.

That is, it is used in the detection of these diseases:

-spine;

- joints;
- brain(brain and spinal cord);
- pituitary gland;
- internal organs;
- mammary glands;

It is necessary to make the MRT device a contrast agent - it is sent through the vessels to clearly see this image. This happens when tumors are diagnosed. The contrast substance accumulates in neoplasms and additionally distinguishes its description. Gadolinium serves as a contrast substance for MRT. It works to lighten the vessels, and is excreted from the body through the kidneys.

Cases when it is impossible to use contrast agent:

- Patients with an allergic reaction to gadolinium;
- Pregnant and lactating women;
- Patients with diabetes mellitus;
- Patients with chronic kidney disease;

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